

TOYLABS

ENABLING AN OPEN INNOVATION MODEL FOR EU TOY INDUSTRY SMES
THROUGH CO-CREATION WITH FABLABS, SAFETY EXPERTS AND CUSTOMER
COMMUNITIES
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Technology Requirements and ToyLabs Components Analysis- v1

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ABBREVIATIONS LIST

ARF	Augmented Reality Feedback
MTA	Market Trend Analysis
MVP	Minimum Viable Product
PMN	Partner Matching and Negotiation
TCP	ToyLabs Core Platform

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable D3.1 titled as "Technology Requirements and ToyLabs Components Analysis-v1" is used to document the preliminary efforts undertaken within the context of Tasks 3.1 (and also 3.2, 3.3 and 3.4), with the aim to identify the requirements of the ToyLabs platform and of its structural components.

Towards this end, the scope of the deliverable at hand is used to collect and analyse the functional and non-functional requirements of the platform. This is achieved by following a well-defined requirements extraction technique, inspired from the agile software development process, adopting the main principles of epics and user stories. The overall methodology is described in the necessary detail and tries to remain at a high level to be understandable by both developers as well as business users, as it is essential to convey the main concepts and requirements to both groups. This will help them validate each envisioned operation of the platform from the very early stages of software design process and assess the platform's added value.

As a result, D3.1, following the prescribed methodology, identifies the main actors, the epics of the overall platform, and matches those to the envisaged components that come out of the work conducted in WP2. As a next step, D3.1 goes on with the identification of the user stories which has been conducted in a collaborative manner between all business, pilot and the technical partners of the consortium. Furthermore, and based on those user stories, the consortium managed to distil a larger list of functional requirements, noting also the importance of each requirement for the overall platform. At the end of the process, non-functional requirements regarding the overall platform have been also identified.

It needs to be note that D3.1 hands over the backlog identified to the next deliverable (D3.2), which will work on their prioritisation and on the definition of the ToyLabs MVP, that will also prescribe the development roadmap. Those steps are also described in the methodology presented in D3.1.

At the end of the tasks that formulated D3.1, the consortium managed to identify **8 actors**, draw **28 Epics**, out those **150 user stories** were defined in order to cover the whole ToyLabs methodology and its tools as they have been defined in deliverable D2.1. These resulted at the end to a list that contained **174 functional** and **12 non-functional requirements**.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Purpose and scope

Deliverable D3.1 titled as "Technology Requirements and ToyLabs Components Analysis-v1" is used to document the preliminary efforts undertaken within the context of Tasks 3.1 (and also 3.2, 3.3 and 3.4), with the aim to identify the requirements of the core ToyLabs platform and of its structural components.

Towards this end, the scope of the deliverable at hand is used to collect and analyse the functional and non-functional requirements of the platform. This is achieved by following a well-defined requirements extraction technique, inspired from the agile software development process, adopting principles of epics and user stories.

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

D3.1 is structured as follows:

- Section 2 presents the overall requirements elicitation methodology, which will steer the activities for all WP3 deliverables
- Section 3 works on the initial identification of the backlog, defining the actors, the epics as well as the user stories of the ToyLabs platform
- Section 4 details the user stories into functional requirements per component, while also the non-functional requirements are presented
- Section 5 concludes the deliverable, stating the next imminent steps to be executed and documented under the upcoming deliverable D3.2

1.3 Relation to other ToyLabs WPs and Tasks

As identified in the DoA, D3.1 is tightly linked to all other WP3 deliverables, as well as to all WP4 Deliverables.

Regarding WP3, D3.1 is tightly linked to D3.2 which succeeds D3.1 with only 1 month difference, and in there the user stories prioritisation, the MVP definition and the architecture design will be performed. These activities, which are all based on the initial content of D3.1 will continue to be executed during the whole course of the project, as ToyLabs relies on an agile approach, with short design and development cycles. Therefore, the continuous closely monitoring of the requirements and their implementation is of outmost importance, as both the development tasks, as well as the piloting tasks are responsible for the continuous validation of the platform features, which may result in changes in the overall backlog that has been identifies in D3.1

Based on the above, D3.1 is evidently linked also to WP4 and all its deliverables, as the latter constitute the prototypes and the software outputs of the project that will formulate the ToyLabs platform.

2 METHODOLOGY FOR REQUIREMENTS ELICITATION

2.1 Why Agile?

ToyLabs is a project that is expected to run for 18 months, after which it aims to deliver an ICT infrastructure that will demand limited further investment and effort to be publicly open and at a market-ready state. The overall attempt is at the same time benefiting from the existence of ready-to-use components that have been identified and will be integrated into the platform, but has also certain challenging tasks that have to do not only with the integration and software development tasks, but more importantly with the understanding of the needs of the end-users and their acceptance of the platform to be delivered.

In this context, ToyLabs will utilise an agile-inspired software development methodology, adapted to the specific needs of the project in order to gradually release value through the platform, based on the continuous and incremental roll-out of the most important and valuable features of the latter.

The work that had been done in WP2, hence the high-level methodology description identified in D2.1, is the basis of initiating this task. By the collaboration between technical partners and pilots both functional and non-functional requirements were pointed out from the user stories.

The overall objective of this activity is to identify the user requirements of the platform, mostly from the end-users (pilots') perspective, in order to develop the best-suited solution that could accommodate the project's pilots and advertise the platform's value as a best case. As the platform is initially conceived as an integrated infrastructure that consists of various (sub) components, the user requirements are split in four main categories, as they also derive out of the work in WP, which namely are:

- Core platform requirements
- Partner Matchmaking Component requirements
- Component Requirements
- AR Feedback Component Requirements

It needs to be noted that this approach allows the introduction of new components in the near future, without necessarily messing with the user requirements of other components, as the overall ToyLabs platform is conceived as a modular, flexible and expandable solution that could accommodate novel concepts that could complement the ones that are already included in the initial concept.

Utilising an Agile methodology has also the advantage of breaking down the risks of implementation in small increments, minimizing the overall software failure risk as acceptance criteria are applied to each incremental release (called sprints), involving

not only developers but the end users as well. The latter, are also involved in the beginning of the overall process, as they are the ones that rank the importance and the value of each user story, thus they are the ones, alongside with the development experts, that decide on the release prioritisation of the elements of the backlog (see below)

2.2 The ToyLabs Development Methodology

As identified above, ToyLabs will utilise an adapted version of the Agile methodology for requirements elicitation, which is in a position to clearly and comprehensively describe the operation of the platform and of its components in an end-user understandable manner, but at the same time present all the necessary technical perspectives that are required by software engineers and developers to formulate the overall platform architecture and specifications.

Figure 1: Agile Development Cycle and its Benefits¹

¹ <http://e5workflow.com/blog/importance-of-agile-in-2016/>

The picture above presents the phases for the definition of the ToyLabs user requirements based on the agile methodology to be executed which is presented briefly in the following subsections.

In the agile development process proposed, functional as well as key non-functional requirements of the software are expressed via the Backlog² (Product Backlog in Scrum³ language), including an ordered list of backlog items. The definition of the backlog is crucial since all requests for building or modifying the products/service are formally expressed as user stories. The methodology considers that the backlog (and consequently all user stories) shall be goal-oriented, i.e. focusing on the "what" rather than the "how".

An important thing to mention is that the Backlog may change/ get updated over time (from one release of a software to the next), so this step can be repeated several times, when user stories are added or amended as a result of a validation or verification process.

2.2.1 Actors Identification

This is the initial task performed concerns the identification of the "actors" that will utilise the platform. These are actors as seen from the perspective of the system, thus a real user (e.g. an individual) may have different roles on the system, resulting in the definition of more than one system actors (for example the same individual can be an "unregistered user" and then become a "registered" user, and be also at the same time an "administrator" if he is given more rights).

However, at this point one does not distinguish internal actors in components to be integrated, but is only concerned about the main "system actors" of the platform as a whole.

2.2.2 Epics and Components Identification

Following the identification of actors, "Epics" are created, which are large concepts that describe (at high-level) operations that a user wishes to do, and those are broken down then in more specific parts, which are called "users stories", which are then released as code in "sprints".

² <https://www.agilealliance.org/glossary/backlog/>

³ [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Scrum_\(software_development\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Scrum_(software_development))

Figure 2: From Epics to Development Tasks⁴

An epic can span over time and sprints, and often it also might change its scope, as the project is progressing, as releases, feedback and operation might hint to alternations of initial ideas and perceived operations.

In the case of ToyLabs, Epics are describing the major operations of the different components (and of the platform) and are utilised to group together user stories in an effort to better structure the overall development backlog.

2.2.3 User Stories' Elicitation

As parts of larger "Epics", "User stories" are smaller idea segments, utilised to provide high-level definitions of requirements, describing a feature told from the end user's perspective, usually a user or customer of the system.

A user story is a short, generally one-sentence, but its power is that it is time self-explanatory and that it contains enough information to describe the requirement, so that the developers can produce a reasonable estimation of the effort to implement it.

ToyLabs adopts the perspective that a User Story is really a well-expressed requirement, which⁵:

⁴ <https://www.atlassian.com/agile/delivery-vehicles>

⁵ <http://dSDM.org/dig-deeper/book/15-requirements-and-user-stories>

- Focuses on the viewpoint of a role who will use or be impacted by the solution
- Defines the requirement in language that has meaning for that role
- Helps to clarify the rationale for the requirement
- Helps to define high level requirements without necessarily going into low level detail too early
- Considers user goals and the business value of each requirement

Typically, user stories are proved in the following manner:

As an < actor role>, I want <action (to do a thing)> so that <reason>.

In an agile project, new or updated user stories are surfacing at any time of implementation, changing the backlog. Such a behaviour is of course desired, as it helps teams to constantly focus on things that matter to users and exclude other features that might not be that important as the value they eventually deliver to both the system and the environment surrounding it. For this purpose, each user story is ranked based on its value and urgency (see section 2.2.5)

#	EPIC	USER STORY					Company		
		As a	ROLE	I want	GOAL/DESIRE	, so that	BENEFIT	Value	Urgency
VI.1	Platform Browsing		Visitor		to find out more about the ToyLabs project from the main platform		I can understand how the project operates	5	5
VI.2	Platform Browsing		Visitor		to go through a short tutorial/help page on how the ToyLabs platform operates		I understand the value and operation principles of the platform	4	4
VI.3	Platform Browsing		Visitor		to view all public products of ToyLabs in the main platform		I can understand which products are supported by the platform	3	3

Figure 3: User Story documentation template

User stories are recorded in a “user story sheet”, often divided by actor, as the one shown in the figure above, that includes the following information:

- ID: an arbitrary ID composed by the actor’s name (2letter) and a number;
- Epic: representing a “group” of user stories, trying to provide a broader context regarding a specific goal of an actor.
- User Story: A textual description, truncated in the following pieces:
 - o *As an <actor role>*: indicating the role of the subject of the story (e.g. the actor identified above) (selection from actor’s list)
 - o *I want <action (to do a thing)>*: the functionality to be added to the solution (free text). This is the core concept of a requirement.
 - o *so that <reason>*: the added value of the development suggested (free text)
- Value: it is the added value (from 1 (lowest) to 5 (highest))
- Urgency: a priority value (from 1 (lowest) to 5 (highest))

To ensure that user stories developed in this step have the required quality and characteristics, a user-story validation process is included into the methodology. The scope of the validation of each user story is to estimate to which extent the user story

covers the INVEST⁶ characteristics, i.e. the six main attributes of a good quality user story, as may be used in a Scrum, Kanban⁷ or Extreme Programming (XP)⁸ project:

- *Independent*: The user story should be self-contained in a way that there is no inherent dependency on another user story.
- *Negotiable*: User stories, up until they are part of an iteration, can always be changed and rewritten.
- *Valuable*: A user story must deliver value to the end user.
- *Estimable*: The team must always be able to estimate the size of a user story.
- *Small*: User stories should not be so big as to become impossible to plan/task/prioritize with a certain level of certainty.
- *Testable*: The user story or its related description must provide the necessary information to make test development possible.

2.2.4 Components Requirements Definition

In most agile methods, the requirements identification stage (especially concerning the function requirements) equals to the identification of user stories, as they possess enough information to help engineers and developers carry on with the implementation tasks.

However, as ToyLabs is a product that highly relies on the successful integration of already developed components, as well as due to the larger footprint of its technical solution than those of simple small programmes, the consortium agreed to conduct a more detailed requirements elicitation process, that describes in more depth the operation of each component.

These requirements come directly out of the user stories identified and constitute a corpus of reference for all development activities of the project, as well as a validation list for cross-checking after the development the smooth operation of each component.

During this step, both the "Functional" and the "Non-Functional" requirements are identified.

⁶ <http://xp123.com/articles/invest-in-good-stories-and-smart-tasks/>

⁷ [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kanban_\(development\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kanban_(development))

⁸ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Extreme_programming

2.2.4.1 Functional Requirements Identification

The identification of those requirements is performed using the following tables.

Component Description

This template documents the main functionalities of the component under examination and acts as an introduction on the main components' features.

Table 1: Component Description Template

Component Description
This component allows the <actor> to <high level description of operation> such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Task 1• Task 2• ...• Task N

Component's Actors

This template identifies the main actors that are engaged with the component under examination.

Table 2: Component Actors Identification Template

Name	Description
User 1	Description of User 1 main roles and operations
User 2	Description of User 2 main roles and operations
...	...
User n	Description of User n main roles and operations

Functional Requirements

Functional Requirements identified as follows:

- *ID: The ID of the Requirement, using a three-letter code relevant to the component's title, and a decimal number. The ID could contain decimal numbers at lower level, to pinpoint requirements linked to "parent" requirements*
- *Name: The name of the requirement*
- *Description: A short textual description of the Requirement*

- *MoSCoW: An identification of the importance of the requirement for the overall platform, following the MoSCoW method (Must have, Should have, Could have or Won't have)⁹*

Table 3: Functional Requirements Identification Template

ID	Name	Description	MoSCoW
<i>MTA.01</i>	<i>Name 1</i>	<i>Description 1</i>	<i>Must/Should/ Could/Won't</i>
<i>QQQ.2</i>	<i>Name 2</i>	<i>Description 2</i>	<i>Must/Should/ Could/Won't</i>
<i>...</i>	<i>...</i>	<i>...</i>	<i>...</i>
<i>QQQ.n</i>	<i>Name n</i>	<i>Description n</i>	<i>Must/Should/ Could/Won't</i>

Component's operation pre-conditions

Preconditions that should exist to allow the operation of the component

- *Precondition PQ.1*
- *Precondition PQ.2*
- *.....*
- *Precondition PQ.X*

2.2.4.2 Non-Functional Requirements Identification

The non-functional requirements identified are platform-wide and are based on the ISO/IEC 25010:2011 model.

Figure 4: ISO/IEC 25010:2011 Software Product Quality model

Per this mode, eight quality characteristics contributing to software product quality are identified, as shown in the previous figure and analysed in the next table.

⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/MoSCoW_method

Table 4: ISO/IEC 25010:2011 Software Product Quality Model Sub-Categories

Quality characteristic	Sub-categories
Functional Suitability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Functional Completeness • Functional Correctness • Functional Appropriateness
Performance Efficiency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time Behaviour • Resource Utilization • Capacity
Compatibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-existence • Interoperability
Usability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Appropriateness Recognisability • Learnability • Operability • User Error Protection • User Interface Aesthetics • Accessibility
Reliability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maturity • Availability • Fault Tolerance • Recoverability
Security	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Confidentiality • Integrity • Non-repudiation • Authenticity • Accountability
Maintainability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Modularity • Reusability • Analysability • Modifiability • Testability
Portability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adaptability • Installability • Replaceability

2.2.5 Backlog Prioritisation

The user stories identified in the previous step constitute the backlog which defines the features that have to be developed by the software teams. In order to construct the

first version and produce an initial working prototype, which will be constantly updated and upgraded with new features, a prioritisation of this back log has to be performed.

The backlog prioritisation can be executed by employing a simple prioritisation model which calculates the value of a user story, against its urgency, as identified by all stakeholders.

This is performed by:

- Calculating, in a qualitative manner the business value of this user story (using a scale between 1-5 points), by asking questions such as:
 - How important is this feature for the overall process?
 - How many users will use it?
 - How often will it be used?

The following table, as proposed by Lant¹⁰ shows the values regarding the business importance.

Table 5: User stories for code quality reviewing, business value dimension

Value	Guidelines
5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extremely Important to most or all customers • Extreme impact on brand or reputation • Critical to the success of the business
4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Important to many customers • Significant impact on brand or reputation • Significant competitive advantage
3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Important to a moderate number of customers • Moderate significant impact on brand or reputation • Moderate important competitive advantage
2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Important to only few customers • Minor impact on brand or reputation • Minor competitive advantage
1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Important to only a few or even no customers • Little or no impact on brand or reputation • Little or no competitive advantage

¹⁰ Michael Lant (2010). How to Easily Prioritize Your Agile Stories. Available at: <http://michaellant.com/2010/05/21/how-to-easily-prioritize-your-agile-stories/>

- Identifying the urgency for the development of each user story, using again a list between 1-5. The following table by Lant, shows the potential values regarding the urgency of a user story.

Table 6: User stories for code quality reviewing, urgency dimension

Value	Guidelines
5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Extremely time constrained. Extreme level of dependency of other items on the completion of this task If not completed immediately there is little or no value to doing it.
4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Highly time constrained High level of dependency of other items on the completion of this task Important to go into the next sprint because of customer or contractual requirements
3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Moderately time constrained Moderate dependency of other items on the completion of this task Desirable to complete in the next one or two sprints
2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Minimally time constrained Minimal dependency of other items on the completion of this task Completion in the next two or three sprints is adequate
1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not time constrained No dependencies Little or no impact

Following this approach, user stories can be ranked and the ones to be included in the MVP are becoming more evident. The multiplication of the Business Value with the Urgency provides a "Priority" indicator which ranges between 1 and 25. The higher this number is, the sooner a user story should be forwarded for implementation.

Figure 5: Priority as a multiplication between Business Value and Urgency

Figure 6: Explaining the priority numbers

It needs to be noted that the final list of user stories is also group by "epics" and "components", in order to identify which of those set should be delivered first. As such, in the ToyLabs development process it can be that a user story that scores higher in general, is delivered after the delivery of another one that scored lower, as the "epic" or the "component" of the latter is deemed more important to release at the early stages.

The overall voting on the user stories is delivered as part of deliverable D3.2.

2.2.6 MVP Definition

MVP stands for "Minimum Viable Product" as is the output that is able to minimize the risk of failure and improve the value generated. An MVP is the version of a product which has the highest return on investment versus risk.

Nevertheless, even if the MVP pinpoints the minimum set of features that are necessary for a product to be deployed and validated, it does not dictate a team to seize their work when reaching that state; on the contrary MVP is a strategy for cutting out unnecessary spending, but being able to quickly learn about the customers and what can be sold to them, resulting in this manner into more viable, profitable and successful products that are gradually improved and populated with extra features.

The MVP of the ToyLabs platform will derive out of the step of voting on the user stories and on selecting the ones that are more important to be implemented during the course of the project.

The ToyLabs MVP will be presented in deliverable D3.2, as per DoA.

3 TOYLABS BACKLOG DEFINITION

3.1 Actors identification

The ToyLabs platform is expected to have the following actors:

Table 7: ToyLabs actors

Actor	Description
Visitor	A user that lands on the ToyLabs platform page and browses the platform without logging in
Ordinary User	A user that is registered in the platform and can access content and features that are not available to visitors
Manufacturer	A user that takes up the role of a manufacturer, who is responsible for creating a product and steering the whole process of the toy creation
FabLab	A user that is representing a FabLab, who can collaborate with Manufacturers
Expert	A user that has a professional capacity as an expert, who can collaborate with Manufacturers and FabLabs. Under this category, both Safety Experts and Childhood Experts are included. Those are different groups, having different business scopes. However, since their envisaged operation in the platform is similar, they are grouped under 1 actor altogether. Emerging user stories during WP3, might lead to the separation of those two sub-types and their eventual distinction as 2 different actors
Product Owner	A user that has initiated the process of creating a product, being either a manufacturer himself, or choosing a manufacturer to delegate design and production to the latter
Organisation Owner	A user that has set up an organisation structure in the platform and is able to manage it
Organisation Member	A user that has join an organisation structure

3.2 Epics and Components Identification

Prior to the analysis of the user requirements through user stories, “Epics” were identified which were conceived to describe the overall operation and services offered by the ToyLabs platform, always in accordance with the ToyLabs methodology. Those “Epics”, were evaluated based on their deployment feasibility having in mind the limited the duration of the ToyLabs project, and are agreed to be the ones that are able to

design an information system that goes hand-in-hand with the methodology and delivers the maximum value of it/ However, it needs to be noted that the proposed ToyLabs methodology is larger in scope than the initially identified "Epics", and therefore the platform is tasked to deliver the core and most important functionality proposed by the methodology, to showcase its significance and added value.

In this context, the following Epics were identified:

- **Platform Browsing:** Each user has to be able to browse the platform and see the main offerings of the project, to understand its value and operation
- **Registration/Log In:** Each visitor to the platform must be able to register to the platform and then enter the platform through a specified login procedure.
- **Profile Editing:** Each user of the platform has his own profile and is able to enter more details regarding his personal and professional data.
- **Organisation Selection:** Each user of the platform has the option to create a new organisation or to ask to join an existing one.
- **ToyLabs Products Browsing:** Each registered platform user, can view more information about the products available in the ToyLabs platform
- **Communication Actions:** Users are able to use direct messages to communicate with each other
- **Feedback Provision:** Users are able to use commenting tools to attach feedback to various artefacts
- **Product Initiation:** Users are able to start the "production creation" process, becoming product owners
- **Prototype Request:** Users would like to request real prototypes to be sent to them by manufacturers
- **Product Handling:** Users should be able to handle the product design and prototyping lifecycle
- **Design Handling:** Users should be able to handle how designs evolve
- **Prototype Handling:** Users should be able to handle how designs evolve
- **Feedback to Design:** Users are able to provide feedback to designs
- **Feedback to Prototype:** Users are able to provide feedback to prototypes
- **Product Information Filling:** Users that manage products should be able to enter data regarding their products
- **Manufacturing Initiation:** Users should be able to initiate the manufacturing processes
- **Product Monitoring:** A user that is handling a product should be able to monitor its creation process.
- **Organisation Information Filling:** A user that is handling an organisation should be able to manage the information regarding the organisations
- **Organisation Management:** A user that is handling an organisation should be able to manage its members

- **Participating in an Organisation:** A user that participates in an organisation should be able to leave and join at any time
- **Partner Matching:** A user that is seeking collaborators should be able to set up a query to search for potential partnerships
- **Contract Negotiation:** A user that has identified a collaboration opportunity should be able to negotiate the terms of collaboration over the platform.
- **FabLab Contract Opportunity:** A FabLab should be able to respond to collaboration requests and take part in partnerships
- **Expert Contract Opportunity:** An Expert should be able to respond to collaboration requests and take part in partnerships
- **Market Trend Analysis Setup:** A user should be able to configure the MTA component to start seeking for knowledge
- **Market Analytics Visualisation:** A user should be able to access the results of the MTA component
- **Prototype AR Enrichment:** Users should be able to enrich AR models with information to be able to collect feedback
- **Prototype AR Feedback Collection:** Users should be able to collect feedback from the ARF component

Based on those Epics, as well as on the different sub-parts of the methodology, the following functional components of the ToyLabs platform have been identified, and were linked with the Epics.

- **TCP (ToyLabs Core Platform).** This is the main infrastructure that powers the ToyLabs platform and is the host environment for all other sub-components that need to be integrated. This component includes the following Epics:
 - Platform Browsing
 - Registration/Log In
 - Profile Editing
 - Organisation Selection
 - ToyLabs Products Browsing
 - Communication Actions
 - Feedback Provision
 - Product Initiation
 - Prototype Request
 - Product Handling
 - Design Handling
 - Prototype Handling
 - Feedback to Design
 - Feedback to Prototype
 - Product Information Filling
 - Manufacturing Initiation

- Product Monitoring
- Organisation Information Filling
- Organisation Management
- Participating in an Organisation
- **PMN (Partner Matching and Negotiation) Component.** This component handles the functions of partner searching and matching between different platform users to enable collaboration opportunities. This component includes the following Epics:
 - Partner Matching
 - Contract Negotiation
 - FabLab Contract Opportunity
 - Expert Contract Opportunity
- **MTA (Market Trend Analysis) Component.** The Market Trend Analysis component is responsible for identifying market trends and information about products from the social web and is used by manufacturers for getting ideas and feedback on their products. This component includes the following Epics:
 - Market Trend Analysis Setup
 - Market Analytics Visualisation
- **ARF (Augmented Reality Feedback) Component.** This is the component that enables users to provide comments of prototypes, based models that are presented to users through Augmented Reality. This component includes the following Epics
 - Prototype AR Enrichment
 - Prototype AR Feedback Collection

3.3 User Stories per Actor

3.3.1 User Stories for Actor “Visitor”

#	EPIC	USER STORY					
		As a	ROLE	I want	GOAL/DESIRE	, so that	BENEFIT
VI.1	Platform Browsing		Visitor		to find out more about the ToyLabs product from the main platform		I can understand how the product operates
VI.2	Platform Browsing		Visitor		to go through a short tutorial/help page on how the ToyLabs platform operates		I understand the value and operation principles of the platform
VI.3	Platform Browsing		Visitor		to view all public products of ToyLabs in the main platform		I can understand which products are supported by the platform
VI.4	Platform Browsing		Visitor		to sort products on the website based on their creation date		I can see the most recent ones
VI.5	Platform Browsing		Visitor		to sort products on the website based on their popularity		
VI.6	Platform Browsing		Visitor		to see a sort description of each product, including the product owners' details, and likes		I can find out more about a product and the organisation behind it
VI.7	Platform Browsing		Visitor		to be able to contact the ToyLabs platform operators through a form		I can make contact with them
VI.8	Platform Browsing		Visitor		to be able to see the terms of use of the platform and the NDA		I can choose whether I want to carry on the registration procedure or not
VI.9	Platform Browsing		Visitor		to be able to change the accessibility settings on the website's content		I can better access information in case I have a disability
VI.10	Platform Browsing		Visitor		to be able to change the website's language		I can view information in my mother language
VI.11	Platform Browsing		Visitor		to be able to see the list of registered users in the platform		I can find possible collaborators
VI.12	Platform Browsing		Visitor		to be able to see the list of registered organisations in the platform		I can find possible collaborating organisations

VI.13	Platform Browsing		Visitor		to display a public AR model of a final product with the help of the ToyLabs AR Engine		I can have a virtual representation of the product in a real setting environment
VI.14	Platform Browsing		Visitor		to provide feedback to AR models in case this is allowed		I can provide my comments without being logged in
VI.15	Registration/Log In		Visitor		to be able to register/log in with minimal details		I can be part of the ToyLabs platform
VI.16	Registration/Log In		Visitor		to be able to use my social network credentials to register/log in		I can be part of the ToyLabs platform
VI.17	Registration/Log In		Visitor		to be able to request a reset of my password		I can set a new one in case I forgot it

3.3.2 User Stories for Actor "Ordinary User"

#	EPIC	USER STORY					
		As a	ROLE	I want	GOAL/DESIRE	, so that	BENEFIT
OU.1	Registration		Ordinary User		to be able to specify some basic, optional personal profile information during the initial registration process		I can have a more complete personal profile
OU.2	Profile Editing		Ordinary User		to be able to choose the role that I will have in ToyLabs (Manufacturer, FabLab, Safety Expert, Childhood Expert, Ordinary User)		I can enjoy the services offered to the role I belong to
OU.3	Profile Editing		Ordinary User		to be able to edit my personal profile information		I can have a more complete personal profile
OU.4	Profile Editing		Ordinary User		to be able to make my profile "private"		I am no longer listed in the public users of the platform
OU.5	Profile Editing		Ordinary User		to be able to permanently remove my account credentials from the system		I can no longer log-in and not be contacted by other users
OU.6	Profile Editing		Ordinary User		to choose whether I can hide my profile details in case this is allowed		I can protect my online identity during feedback
OU.7	Profile Editing		Ordinary User		I want to be able to ask for becoming validated by the ToyLabs platform		I can become a trusted collaborator

OU.8	Organisation Selection		Ordinary User		during the registration process to be able to specify a new Organisation that I belong to in case this does not exist		I can add my organisation to the platform and become the Owner of it
OU.9	Organisation Selection		Ordinary User		during the registration process to my Organisation to provide the basic information of the entity		an informative profile of my Organisation becomes available to all
OU.10	Organisation Selection		Ordinary User		during the registration process to my Organisation to provide the extended capability information of the entity		a detailed profile of my Organisation's capabilities becomes available to all
OU.11	Organisation Selection		Ordinary User		during the registration process to be able to join an existing organisation, pending the approval of its Owner		I can collaborate with my co-workers of the same organisation
OU.12	Organisation Selection		Ordinary User		register my Organisation if not already done during registration		I can add my organisation to the platform and become the Owner of it
OU.13	Organisation Selection		Ordinary User		to be able to join an existing organisation, pending the approval of its Owner		I can collaborate with my co-workers of the same organisation
OU.14	Organisation Selection		Ordinary User		to be able to leave an already joined organisation		I can no longer see the detailed products of it
OU.15	ToyLabs Products Browsing		Ordinary User		to sort public designs on the website based on their creation date		I can see the most recent ones
OU.16	ToyLabs Products Browsing		Ordinary User		to sort public designs on the website based on their popularity		I can see the ones with the most comments
OU.17	ToyLabs Products Browsing		Ordinary User		to sort public prototypes on the website based on their creation date		I can see the most recent ones
OU.18	ToyLabs Products Browsing		Ordinary User		to sort public prototypes on the website based on their popularity		I can see the ones with the most comments
OU.19	ToyLabs Products Browsing		Ordinary User		to be able to "follow" a product to add it to my Favourites by hitting "like"		I can receive updates about this product in the future
OU.20	ToyLabs Products Browsing		Ordinary User		to be able to view my "Followed" products in a separate screen		I can focus on them
OU.21	ToyLabs Products Browsing		Ordinary User		to be able to share information about a product on my social media accounts		so that I further disseminate information about a product
OU.22	Communication Actions		Ordinary User		to be able to send a direct message to the Organisation behind a product		I establish a communication channel with an Organisation

OU.23	Communication Actions		Ordinary User	to be able to view messages sent to me and reply	I can continue communication with an Organisation/ other users
OU.24	Communication Actions		Ordinary User	to get notified when I have a direct message received	I know a response to my request was provided
OU.25	Communication Actions		Ordinary User	to get notified when a product makes an announcement to its followers	I get instant news directly from the product's Organisation
OU.26	Feedback Provision		Ordinary User	to comment on a product and take part in an ongoing discussion	to make my opinion heard
OU.27	Feedback Provision		Ordinary User	to comment on a public AR model in the ToyLabs platform	I can provide Feedback back to the manufacturer
OU.28	Feedback Provision		Ordinary User	to vote specific features on a public AR model, on my mobile device	I can instantly provide feedback
OU.29	Feedback Provision		Ordinary User	to upload a screenshot of the public AR model	I can show to the manufacturer my display of the model
OU.30	Product Initiation		Ordinary User	to be able to initiate a product creation phase	I can become a product owner
OU.31	Prototype Request		Ordinary User	to be able to request a prototype of a product	I can have a hands-on experience

3.3.3 User Stories for Actor “Manufacturer”

#	EPIC	USER STORY					
		As a	ROLE	I want	GOAL/DESIRE	, so that	BENEFIT
MA.1	Manufacturer Contract Opportunity		Manufacturer		to be able to view invitations from product owners for new product's creations		get notified on whether I have been selected as a manufacturer
MA.2	Manufacturer Contract Opportunity		Manufacturer		to be able to reply positive and sign a NDA or negative to product creation invitation		I can notify the product owner of my decision
MA.3	Manufacturer Contract Opportunity		Manufacturer		to retrieve, sign and send back a contract sent to me by a product owner		I can then start the production process

MA.4	Product Handling		Manufacturer	to be able to see a list of all products I am handling		I can select details on specific ones
MA.5	Partner Matching		Manufacturer	to be able to initiate the partner matching module and search for partners		I can select other collaborators to work with
MA.6	Partner Matching		Manufacturer	to see a list of collaborators suggested by partners I already work with		I can build a more trusted cycle of collaboration
MA.7	Partner Matching		Manufacturer	to invite a partner to a step of the toy creation process (Design/Prototype/Mass Creation)		I can explore collaboration opportunities
MA.8	Partner Matching		Manufacturer	to include an NDA to the invitation from the Partner Matching module to a specific toy creation process		I can protect my IPRs in that process
MA.9	Partner Matching		Manufacturer	see all partners that have signed an NDA to a product		I know with who I am sharing information
MA.10	Partner Matching		Manufacturer	to launch an "Open Request" call for Collaborators		I can attract those interested to collaborate with me
MA.11	Partner Matching		Manufacturer	to attach to the "Open Request" call an NDA		I can protect my IPRs
MA.12	Partner Matching		Manufacturer	to view responses from partners that responded to the "Open Request" and signed the NDA contract		I can evaluate which ones to accept
MA.13	Partner Matching		Manufacturer	to select which partners from the "Open Request" process to invite to the toy creation process step		I can select other collaborators to work with
MA.14	Partner Matching		Manufacturer	to decline responses from the "Open Request" process		I can filter out responses that are not interesting to me
MA.15	Contract Negotiation		Manufacturer	see all partners that have signed an NDA to a product		I know with who I am sharing information
MA.16	Contract Negotiation		Manufacturer	to send a contract to a collaborator already added to a toy creation process step (have signed the NDA)		I can formally engage with him
MA.17	Contract Negotiation		Manufacturer	accept (double sign) a signed contract from a collaborator		I have a trusted and formal relationship with him
MA.18	Contract Negotiation		Manufacturer	see all partners that have signed a collaboration contract to a product		I know with whom I have an open contract in a product

MA.19	Market Trend Analysis Setup		Manufacturer	to be able to initiate the sentiment analysis module		I can understand the sentiment of users on a product or a manufacturer and trends discussed in web2.0 channels
MA.20	Market Trend Analysis Setup		Manufacturer	to be able to initiate the trend analysis module		Understanding of trends in toy sector, using web2.0 channels
MA.21	Market Trend Analysis Setup		Manufacturer	to select the social media channels to be used by the sentiment or the trend analysis module		I can understand the opinion or the desire of the crowd in the web
MA.22	Market Trend Analysis Setup		Manufacturer	to select the other web sources (blogs/forums/pages) to be used by the sentiment or trends analysis module		I can understand sentiments, desires and opinions in specific blogs and web pages
MA.23	Market Trend Analysis Setup		Manufacturer	to select specific words in the sentiment or trends analysis module		these are used for mining the web
MA.24	Market Trend Analysis Setup		Manufacturer	to enable the "influencers' mode" of the sentiment analysis module		I can find people with influencing power in a broad web audience on a specific topic
MA.25	Market Analytics Visualisation		Manufacturer	to see the positive, negative and other online comments on my product or my brand from the sentiment analysis module		I can define a strategy for improvement
MA.26	Market Analytics Visualisation			to see visualised analytics based on the results of the sentiment or the trend analysis module		I can better understand the results of the module
MA.27	Market Analytics Visualisation		Manufacturer	to see related concepts about search terms		Related concepts to search terms may can drive to results about trends and feedback from users
MA.28	Design handling		Manufacturer	to create a new "Master" Design		I can have multiple versions of the same master design
MA.29	Design handling		Manufacturer	to create a new "Design" version		I can open up the design phase of the process
MA.30	Design handling		Manufacturer	to be able to turn the visibility of a "Design" version to public, that will showcase only basic design information		it can be displayed publicly in the ToyLabs showcase page

MA.31	Design handling		Manufacturer	to populate the "Design" version with material relevant to this phase (files, specification, cost analyses, etc.)	I can share this information with my future collaborators
MA.32	Design handling		Manufacturer	to view the feedback of my collaborators on a "Design" version	I can fine tune my idea
MA.33	Design handling		Manufacturer	to close a "Design" version	I can move on to another phase or publish an updated design
MA.34	Prototype handling		Manufacturer	to open a new "Design" version once the previous one is closed	I work with my collaborators on the improved design that resulted from the previous thread
MA.35	Prototype handling		Manufacturer	to create a new "Prototype"	I can open up the prototyping phase of the process
MA.36	Prototype handling		Manufacturer	to be able to turn the visibility of a "Prototype" version to public, that will showcase only basic design information	it can be displayed publicly in the ToyLabs showcase page
MA.37	Prototype handling		Manufacturer	to populate the "prototype" version with material relevant to this phase (files, specification, cost analyses, etc.)	I can share this information with my future collaborators
MA.38	Prototype AR Enrichment		Manufacturer	to attach an AR model to a prototype	I can share it with collaborators
MA.39	Prototype AR Enrichment		Manufacturer	to accompany the AR model with a simple questionnaire for AR user	they can instantly provide comment from the AR devices
MA.40	Prototype AR Enrichment		Manufacturer	to view the feedback of my collaborators on a "Prototype" version	I can better understand the feedback from the prototype
MA.41	Prototype AR Enrichment		Manufacturer	to view feedback captured from the AR model	I can better understand the feedback from the prototype
MA.42	Prototype AR Enrichment		Manufacturer	to set the privacy category level allowed for AR feedback	I can declare what kind of feedback I welcome (anonymised or not)

3.3.4 User Stories for Actor "FabLab"

#	EPIC	USER STORY					
		As a	ROLE	I want	GOAL/DESIRE	, so that	BENEFIT
FA.1	Fablab Contract Opportunity		FabLab		to get notified about a direct invite I might get from a manufacturer		I can reply to him
FA.2	Fablab Contract Opportunity		FabLab		to browse through "Open Request" call published by manufacturer		I can find new business opportunities
FA.3	Contract Negotiation		FabLab		to be in a position to accept/reject a direct invitation by signing the NDA		I can become a collaborator
FA.4	Contract Negotiation		FabLab		to sign a contract, sent to me by a manufacturer		I can ensure that there is a relationship of trust
FA.5	Fablab Contract Opportunity		FabLab		to positively reply to "Open Request" calls and sign the NDA attached		I can declare my intention to become a collaborator
FA.6	Feedback to Designs		FabLab		to be able to download all material in a "Design" version I have been invited to		I can better understand the design
FA.7	Feedback to Designs		FabLab		to comment (and attach files) on the overall issues of a "Design" version I have been invited to		I can provide my input in terms of updated material back to the thread
FA.8	Feedback to Designs		FabLab		to directly and privately contact a manufacturer about a design version		I can establish a private communication channel
FA.9	Feedback to Prototypes		FabLab		to be able to download all material in a "Prototype" I have been invited to		I can better understand the design
FA.10	Feedback to Prototypes		FabLab		to comment (and attach files) on the overall issues of a "Prototype" I have been invited to		I can provide my input in terms of updated material back to the thread
FA.11	Feedback to Prototypes		FabLab		to directly and privately contact a manufacturer about a prototype		I can establish a private communication channel
FA.12	Feedback to Prototypes		FabLab		to be able to play with controls embed in the AR model		I can have a better experience with the conceptual model
FA.13	Feedback to Prototypes		FabLab		to comment on an AR model in the ToyLabs platform		I can provide Feedback back to the manufacturer
FA.14	Feedback to Prototypes		FabLab		to vote specific features on an AR model, on my mobile device		I can instantly provide feedback
FA.15	Feedback to Prototypes		FabLab		to upload a screenshot of the AR model		I can show to the manufacturer my display of the model

FA.16	Feedback to Prototypes	FabLab	to be able to suggest partners I have collaborated with in the past	I can indicate to manufacturers collaborates I have good experience with
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3.3.5 User Stories for Actor "Expert"

#	EPIC	USER STORY					
		As a	ROLE	I want	GOAL/DESIRE	, so that	BENEFIT
FA.1	Expert Contract Opportunity		Expert		to get notified about a direct invite I might get from a manufacturer		I can reply to him
FA.2	Expert Contract Opportunity		Expert		to browse through "Open Request" call published by manufacturer		I can find new business opportunities
FA.3	Expert Contract Opportunity		Expert		to positively reply to "Open Request" calls and sign the NDA attached		I can declare my intention to become a collaborator
FA.4	Contract Negotiation		Expert		to be in a position to accept/reject a direct invitation by signing the NDA		I can become a collaborator
FA.5	Contract Negotiation		Expert		to sign a contract, send to me by a manufacturer		I can ensure that there is a relationship of trust
FA.6	Feedback to Designs		Expert		to be able to download all material in a "Design" version I have been invited to		I can better understand the design
FA.7	Feedback to Designs		Expert		to comment (and attach files) on the overall issues of a "Design" version I have been invited to		I can provide my input in terms of updated material back to the thread
FA.8	Feedback to Designs		Expert		to directly and privately contact a manufacturer about a design version		I can establish a private communication channel
FA.9	Feedback to Prototypes		Expert		to be able to download all material in a "Prototype" I have been invited to		I can better understand the design
FA.10	Feedback to Prototypes		Expert		to comment (and attach files) on the overall issues of a "Prototype" I have been invited to		I can provide my input in terms of updated material back to the thread
FA.11	Feedback to Prototypes		Expert		to directly and privately contact a manufacturer about a prototype		I can establish a private communication channel
FA.12	Feedback to Prototypes		Expert		to comment on an AR model in the ToyLabs platform		I can provide Feedback back to the manufacturer

FA.13	Feedback to Prototypes	Expert	to vote specific features on an AR model, on my mobile device	I can instantly provide feedback
FA.14	Feedback to Prototypes	Expert	to upload a screenshot of the AR model	I can show to the manufacturer my display of the model

3.3.6 User Stories for Actor "Product Owner"

#	EPIC	USER STORY					
		As a	ROLE	I want	GOAL/DESIRE	, so that	BENEFIT
PO.1	Product Information Filling		Product Owner		to be able to fill in the basic information about a new product		I can provide more details on that product
PO.2	Product Information Filling		Product Owner		to issue announcements about my product		I can notify people of important news
PO.3	Product Information Filling		Product Owner		engage in discussions with users of the platform based on my product		I can get online, direct feedback
PO.4	Product Information Filling		Product Owner		to mark a product as released and update its description		users can find more information about it in the public website
PO.5	Product Information Filling		Product Owner		to specify crucial information about my product (like cost, technical requirements, material requirements, etc.) about my product		I can have a thorough description of my product's specifications
PO.6	Product Information Filling		Product Owner		to archive a finished product		it is not displayed on my dashboard
PO.7	Product Information Filling		Product Owner		to specify whether a product belongs to an organisation I am part of or not		I can distinguish ownership between individuals and organisations
PO.8	Manufacturing Initiation		Product Owner		to choose whether I will create the product on my own or will delegate the manufacturing process		I can become a "manufacturer" or I can have global visibility over the selected manufacturer actions

PO.9	Manufacturing Initiation		Product Owner		to be able to search for a Manufacturer in the platform using the partner matching module		to assign him the responsibility to create my product
PO.10	Manufacturing Initiation		Product Owner		to be able to accompany the invitation to a manufacturer with an NDA		I can protect the IPRs of my idea
PO.11	Manufacturing Initiation		Product Owner		to send a contract to a manufacturer (who has signed the NDA)		I can formally engage with him
PO.12	Manufacturing Initiation		Product Owner		accept (double sign) a signed contract from the manufacturer		I have a trusted and formal relationship with him
PO.13	Product Monitoring		Product Owner		to monitor the overall creation process of a product		I can understand to which state it is
PO.14	Product Monitoring		Product Owner		to view all information on the product, as selected by the manufacturer		I can have a more detailed view on the different actions and decisions
PO.15	Product Monitoring		Product Owner		to be able to see a list of all my products		I can select details on specific ones

3.3.7 User Stories for Actor "Organisation Owner"

#	EPIC	USER STORY					
		As a	ROLE	I want	GOAL/DESIRE	, so that	BENEFIT
OO.1	Organisation Information Filling		Organisation Owner		to be able to edit the basic information about my Organisation		an informative profile of my Organisation becomes available to all
OO.2	Organisation Information Filling		Organisation Owner		to be able to edit the extended capability information of my Organisation		a detailed profile of my Organisation's capabilities becomes available to all
OO.3	Organisation Information Filling		Organisation Owner		to be able to share information about my Organisation through my social media accounts		so that I further disseminate information about my Organisation
OO.4	Organisation Information Filling		Organisation Owner		to be able to make my organisation's profile "private"		it is no longer listed in the public organisations list of the platform
OO.5	Organisation Information Filling		Organisation Owner		to be able to make my organisation's profile "public" (default option)		it is listed in the public organisations list of the platform

OO.6	Organisation Management		Organisation Owner		to get notifications about people asking to join/leave/accept or reject Ownership transfer of my Organisation		I can have an idea on who is a member of my organisation
OO.7	Organisation Management		Organisation Owner		to accept or reject invitations of other people wanting to join my Organisation		I can have all my team online to collaborate
OO.8	Organisation Management		Organisation Owner		to delete my organisation		it is no longer part of the ToyLabs platform
OO.9	Organisation Management		Organisation Owner		to invite other team members to join ToyLabs and my Organisation		I can have all my team online to collaborate
OO.10	Organisation Management		Organisation Owner		to be able to remove users from my Organisation		I can manage the access of users to my Organisation's information
OO.11	Organisation Management		Organisation Owner		to be able to transfer the ownership to another member of the organisation		I can leave Ownership to another user

3.3.8 User Stories for Actor “Organisation Member”

#	EPIC	USER STORY					
		As a	ROLE	I want	GOAL/DESIRE	, so that	BENEFIT
OM.1	Participating in an Organisation		Organisation Member		to be able to leave an Organisation		I no longer see the data
OM.2	Participating in an Organisation		Organisation Member		to be able to accept the transfer of the ownership of an Organisation to my Name		I can become the Owner of it
OM.3	Participating in an Organisation		Organisation Member		to be able to reject the transfer of the ownership of an Organisation to my Name		I remain as a simple member of it
OM.4	Participating in an Organisation		Organisation Member		to be able to share information about my Organisation through my social media accounts		so that I further disseminate information about my Organisation

4 REQUIREMENTS DOCUMENTATION

4.1 Functional Requirements

The functional requirements for the overall ToyLabs infrastructure are identified per component, in order to describe all aspects of functionality of each examined component, so the expected component behaviour can be validated, developed, and tested throughout the development life-cycle.

The requirements identification documentation must be kept updated to support the generation of end-user documentation and to support future maintenance activities. For ToyLabs, the templates that are identified below are used for the initial identification of the functional and non-functional user requirements. In the next steps of the development processes, those placeholders will be used to transfer the necessary information to the development team, while new templates will be created for analysing further aspects, such as the flow of information, the data artefacts, etc. However, those are not part of the initial requirements identification steps described in the document at hand.

4.1.1 Core Platform Requirements

Component Description

This component allows users of the platform to:

- get registered to ToyLabs and obtain a certain role in the system
- Initiate the process of designing and prototyping new products
- Exchange information and knowledge between themselves
- bring up the other components of the system (for Partner Matching and Negotiation, Market Trend Analysis, Augmented Reality Feedback)

4.1.1.1 Component's Actors

The actors of the core platform, are the same as the ones identified in section 3.1. It is noted that in the Functional Requirement presented below, actions that are attributed to visitors and ordinary users (like shorting the product showcase), are also available (and formulate the same requirements) for the other actors as well, however they are not documented in the table below, for reasons of brevity.

4.1.1.2 Functional Requirements

ID	Name	Description	MoSCoW
TCP.01	Products showcase	The system to display all public products	Must

TCP.02	NDA and ToR	The system to display the platform's NDA and Terms & Conditions documents	Must
TCP.03	Multilingualism	The system to display the website's content in other languages (Spanish, Italian, Romania, Greek) than English	Could
TCP.04	Accessibility	The system to provide accessibility features to the visitor	Could
TCP.05	List of Registered Organisations	The system to display a list of registered organisations in the platform	Should
TCP.06	List of Registered Organisations	The system to display a list of registered users in the platform	Could
TCP.07	Showcase Sorting	The Visitor to sort public product based on criteria	Must
TCP.07.01	Showcase sorting by date	The Visitor to sort public product based on creation date	Must
TCP.07.02	Showcase sorting by comments	The Visitor to sort public product based on comments	Could
TCP.07.03	Showcase sorting by likes	The Visitor to sort public product based on popularity	Could
TCP.08	Product Details	The Visitor to see more details about a product	Must
TCP.09	AR Download	The Visitor to be able to download an AR model posted to a product	Should
TCP.10	Simple Signup	The Visitor to be able to register with his email	Must
TCP.10.1	Social Signup	The Visitor to be able to register with his social media accounts	Could
TCP.11	Login	The Visitor to be able to login with his email	Must
TCP.11.1	Social Login	The Visitor to be able to login with his social media accounts	Could
TCP.13	Password Reminder	The Visitor to be able to request his password to be rest	Should
TCP.14	Profile Filling	The Ordinary User to be able to fill in his profile information	Must
TCP.14.1	Profile Editing	The Ordinary User to be able to edit his profile information	Must

TCP.14.2	Profile Visibility	The Ordinary User to make his profile private	Could
TCP.15	Account Removal	The Ordinary User to remove his account from the system	Could
TCP.16	Profile Validation	The Ordinary User to ask for validation by ToyLabs	Won't
TCP.17	Organisation Creation	The Ordinary User to create a new Organisation	Must
TCP.18	Organisation Profile	The Organisation Owner to fill in the information about his organisation	Must
TCP.18.1	Organisation Profile Editing	The Organisation Owner to edit the stored information about his organisation	Should
TCP.18.2	Organisation Profile Visibility	The Organisation Owner to turn the visibility of an Organisation private/public	Could
TCP.19	Joining Organisations	The Ordinary User to ask to join an existing Organisation	Should
TCP.20	Organisation Join Request Notification	The system to notify the Organisation Owner for a join request	Should
TCP.21	Organisation Join Request View	The Organisation Owner to view the join request	Should
TCP.22	Organisation Join Request Response	The Organisation Owner to accept/reject the join Request	Should
TCP.23	Organisation Member Removal	The Organisation Owner to remove a user from the organisation	Could
TCP.24	Organisation Membership Transfer	The Organisation Owner to transfer the ownership to another Organisation Member	Won't
TCP.25	Organisation Member Leaving	The Organisation Member to leave an organisation he has joined	Should
TCP.26	Notifications	The Ordinary User to see notifications of any kind	Must
TCP.27	Sending Direct Message to User	The Ordinary User to send direct messages to other users in the platform	Must
TCP.28	Sending Direct Message to User	The Ordinary User to send direct messages to other Organisations in the platform	Should

TCP.28.01	Routing of Message to Organisation Owner	The System to send the direct message to an Organisation to the Organisation owner	Must
TCP.29	Inbox view	The Ordinary User to view incoming direct messages	Must
TCP.30	Direct Message Reply	The Ordinary User to respond to direct messages he receives	Should
TCP.31	Product Details	The Ordinary User to see more details about a product	Must
TCP.32	User Comments on Product	The Ordinary User to comment on a product	Must
TCP.33	User Comments on Design	The Ordinary User to comment on a design	Must
TCP.34	User Comments on Prototype	The Ordinary User to comment on a prototype	Must
TCP.35	Follow a Product	The Ordinary User to "Follow" a product	Could
TCP.36	Share a Product in Social Media	The Ordinary User to share a product on his social media accounts	Could
TCP.37	Request Real Prototype	The Ordinary User to request to receive a tangible prototype of a product	Could
TCP.38	Product KickOff by User	The Ordinary User to initiate the creation of a product	Should
TCP.39	Product KickOff by Manufacturer	The Manufacturer to initiate the creation of a product	Must
TCP.40	PMN Component	The Manufacturer to launch the PMN component	Must
TCP.41	MTA Component	The Manufacturer to launch the MTA component	Must
TCP.42	ARF Component	The Manufacturer to launch the ARF component	Must
TCP.43	Master Design	The Manufacturer to create "Master" Design	Must
TCP.44	Design Versions	The Manufacturer to create a new Design version	Must
TCP.45	Delete a Design Version	The Manufacturer to delete a Design version	Could
TCP.46	Close a Design Version	The Manufacturer to close a Design version	Should

TCP.47	Design Visibility	The Manufacturer to turn a Design public or private	Should
TCP.48	Design Information	The Manufacturer to fill in information to accompany the Design	Must
TCP.48.1	Design Edit	The Manufacturer to edit information of a Design	Must
TCP.49	Prototype Creation	The Manufacturer to create a Prototype	Must
TCP.50	Prototype Deletion	The Manufacturer to delete a Prototype	Should
TCP.51	Prototype Visibility	The Manufacturer to turn a Prototype public or private	Should
TCP.52	Prototype Information	The Manufacturer to fill in information to accompany the Prototype	Must
TCP.52.1	Prototype Edit	The Manufacturer to edit information of a Prototype	Must
TCP.53	Prototype to AR Link	The system to link the ARF component to a prototype	Must
TCP.54	FabLab Comments on Product	The FabLab to provide comments on a Design	Must
TCP.55	FabLab Comments on Design	The FabLab to upload documents to a Design	Should
TCP.56	FabLab Comments on Prototype	The FabLab to provide comments on a Prototype	Must
TCP.57	Collaborators Suggestions	The FabLab to suggest collaborators to a Manufacturer	Won't
TCP.58	Expert Comments on Product	The Expert to provide comments on a Design	Must
TCP.59	Expert Comments on Design	The Expert to upload documents to a Design	Should
TCP.60	Expert Comments on Prototype	The Expert to provide comments on a Prototype	Must
TCP.61	Product Information Filling	The Product Owner to fill in information about a product	Must

TCP.62	Product Announcement	The Product Owner to send announcements to the product's followers	Could
TCP.63	Product Production Delegation	The Product Owner to delegate production to a manufacturer	Should
TCP.64	Product Monitoring	The Product Owner to view the progress of a Product	Should
TCP.65	Own Product Listing	The Product Owner to see a list of his Products	Must

4.1.1.3 Component's operation pre-conditions

- N/A

4.1.2 Partner Matching and Negotiation Component Requirements

Component Description

This component allows the user of the platform that would like to establish collaborations with each other to:

- seek for collaborators based on specific criteria out from a pool of users
- get recommendations from the system regarding possible collaborators based on specific thresholds
- send specific collaboration requests to other users identified through the search results
- exchange contracts to seal an agreement for collaboration

4.1.2.1 Component's Actors

Name	Description
Seeking User	The user who triggers this component and who is willing to search for collaborators with the help of the component
Matched Partner	The user that is identified by a query ran by the "seeking user" and is suggested as a partner match to carry on the collaboration.

4.1.2.2 Functional Requirements

ID	Name	Description	MoSCoW
PMN.01	Partner Search	The Seeking User to initiate a search session	Must
PMN.01.01	Partner Type Specification	The Seeking User to specify the type of partner he is looking for	Must

PMN.01.02	Search Criteria	The Seeking User to select from a list of partner type-specific filter	Must
PMN.01.03	Query Storing	The Seeking User to save his query as a template query	Could
PMN.01.04	Query Editing	The Seeking User to edit his query by changing his options	Could
PMN.01.05	Query Deletion	The Seeking User to delete a saved template query	Could
PMN.02	System Query Logging	The system to save the query alongside with information on who ordered it	Could
PMN.03	Query Results	The system to present the partner matching results to the Seeking user	Must
PMN.04	Query Results Sorting	The Seeking User to sort the results based on various criteria	Should
PMN.05	Partner Information Browsing	The Seeking User to view details for each result row retrieved	Must
PMN.06	Partner Selection	The Seeking User to select a collaborator out of the list for sending an invitation	Must
PMN.07	NDA Browsing	The Seeking User view the default NDA to be attached to the collaboration invitation	Must
PMN.07.01	NDA editing	The Seeking User to edit the default NDA to be attached to the collaboration invitation	Should
PMN.08	Invitation Expiry Setting	The Seeking User to set an expiry date for the invitation	Could
PMN.08.01	Invitation Termination due to not timely response	The system to automatically destroy the invitation upon expiry of the deadline	Could
PMN.09	Invitation Notification	The system to send a notification to a selected collaborator about an invitation	Must
PMN.10	Invitation Notification Browsing	The matched partner to view a notification	Must
PMN.11	View NDA	The matched partner to view the NDA attached to the invitation	Must
PMN.12	Respond to Invitation	The matched partner to respond to a notification positive or negative	Must

PMN.13	Signature of NDA	The system to sign the NDA on behalf of the matched partner in case his response to an invitation is positive	Should
PMN.14	Notification of invitation acceptance	The system to notify the Seeking User regarding the acceptance/rejection of his invitation from a Matched Partner	Must
PMN.15	View NDA signatories	The Seeking User to view the Matched Partners that have signed an NDA	Must
PMN.15.01	View NDA signatories to a design	The Seeking User to view the Matched Partners that have signed an NDA to a product design	Must
PMN.15.02	View NDA signatories to a prototype	The Seeking User to view the Matched Partners that have signed an NDA to a product prototype	Must
PMN.16	Attaching collaboration contract	The Seeking User to attached a collaboration contract document to be sent to a match partner for a design or a prototype	Should
PMN.17	Setting collaboration contract signature deadline	The Seeking User to set an expiry date for the contract signature	Could
PMN.17.01	Collaboration Contract Termination due to not timely signature	The system to automatically destroy the contract request upon expiry of the deadline	Could
PMN.18	Collaboration Contract notification	The system to notify the Matched Partner that a collaboration contract document is waiting for his signature	Should
PMN.19	Signed Collaboration Contract Return	The Matched Partner to send back the signed collaboration contract document to the Seeking User	Should
PMN.20	Signed Collaboration Contract Notification	The system to notify the Seeking User that a collaboration contract document is waiting for his signature	Should
PMN.21	Storing of Active Contract	The Seeking User to sign the collaboration contract document and upload it in the platform	Must
PMN.22	Active Contract Notification	The system to notify the Matched Partner that a collaboration contract document has been signed by both parties	Must

PMN.23	View active contracts	The Seeking User to view the Matched Partners that have signed a contact	Must
PMN.23.01	View active contracts for a design	The Seeking User to view the Matched Partners that have signed a contract to a product design	Must
PMN.23.02	View active contracts for a prototype	The Seeking User to view the Matched Partners that have signed a contract to a product prototype	Must
PMN.24	Open Request Launch	The Seeking User to launch an Open Request session for partner matching	Should
PMN.24.01	Open Request Partner Type Specification	The Seeking User to specify the partner type he is looking in the Open Request session	Should
PMN.24.02	Open Request Search Criteria	The Seeking User to specify certain partner-type specific criteria he is looking for in the Open Request session	Should
PMN.25	Open Request Matchmaking	The system to automatically match the Open Request with specific candidates	Could
PMN.26	Open Request Notifications	The system to send notifications to the identified candidates (matched partners)	Should
PMN.27	Open Request Response	The Matched partners to respond positive/negative to an Open Request	Should
PMN.28	Open Request NDA signature	The system to sign the NDA on behalf of the matched partner in case his response to an invitation is positive	Could
PMN.29	Notification of Open Request invitation responses	The system to notify the Seeking User regarding the acceptance/rejection of his invitation from a Matched Partner	Should
PMN.30	Acceptance/Rejection of Open Request collaboration intention	The Seeking User to accept/reject the collaboration intention offer by a Matched Partner	Should
PMN.31	Notification of Open Request intention acceptance/rejection	The system to notify the Matched Partner regarding his collaboration intention acceptance by a Seeking User	Should

4.1.2.3 Component's operation pre-conditions

- Partners with rich profile information
- Notification system in place

- Document exchange and communication system in place

4.1.3 Market Trend Analysis Component Requirements

Component Description

This component allows the partner to perform multiple user-selected tasks such as:

- Initialize process of data harvesting
- Trend Analysis
- Social Feedback Analysis

4.1.3.1 Component's Actors

Name	Description
Ordinary User	User with limited rights to component. Ordinary user can use specific features which not require a lot of computational power and thus many computational resources.
Certified User	User with full rights to component. Certified user can use all features of component.

4.1.3.2 Functional Requirements

ID	Name	Description	MoSCoW
MTA.01	User Identification	The system to identify the user's role and his rights to component. If user has limited rights to component, the system to allow him to use specific component' functionalities.	Must
MTA.02	Initialize data harvester	The user called by the system to provide a group of settings, in order to initialize data harvester.	Must
MTA.02.01	Specify keywords or hashtags for harvesting	The system to enable the user to specify the keywords and/or the hashtags that must be included in the collected comments or tweets.	Must
MTA.02.02	Specify products or manufacturer for harvesting	The system to enable the user to specify the products and/or the manufacturers that will relate with the collecting data.	Must
MTA.02.03	Specify social media - web sources for harvesting	The system to enable the user to specify which social media wants as data sources for harvesting.	Must

MTA.02.04	MTA.02.04 Specify the languages of harvesting data	The system to enable the user to specify the language/languages of harvesting data. At first component's supported languages will be English and Spanish.	Should
MTA.02.05	Specify allowable publication dates of harvesting data	The system to enable the user to specify allowable publication dates for data will be collected.	Must
MTA.03	Select Social Type Analysis	The system to enable the user to choose between two types of social network analysis: i) Trend Detection Analysis ii) Social Feedback Analysis	Must
MTA.04	Clean Data	The system to clean or filter the data and process them to obtain a form suitable for the application of analysis algorithms.	Should
MTA.05	Grouping related concepts	The system to identify relevant concepts (e.g. using concept lexicons) and be able to process them combined.	Could
MTA.06	Sentiment Classification	The system for sentiment analysis to calculate the results based on specific emotions. These emotions are: i) anger ii) sadness iii) happiness iv) neutral	Should
MTA.07	Trend Analysis	The system with input part or all harvesting data, to analyse trends.	Must
MTA.07.01	Select part of harvesting data for trend analysis	The system to enable the user to select part of harvesting data in order to begin a trend analysis.	Must
MTA.07.01.01	Select data for trend analysis which include specific keywords and/or hashtags	The system to enable the user to select part of harvesting data which include specific keywords and/or hashtags.	Must
MTA.07.01.02	Select data in specific languages for trend analysis	The system to enable the user to select part of harvesting data which are in specific language/languages.	Should
MTA.07.01.03	Select data for trend analysis which derived from specific social media - web sources	The system to enable the user to select part of harvesting data which derived from specific social media. The social media are subset of social media to MTA.02.03.	Must

MTA.07.01.04	Select data for trend analysis which have specific publication dates	The system to enable the user to select part of harvesting data which have specific publication dates. These publication dates are subset of publication dates to MTA.02.05.	Must
MTA.07.01.05	Enable/Disable Influencer Mode	The system to enable the user to choose if he wants, or not, for trend analysis to be considered part of harvesting data, which come from specific social accounts with a big influence on toy industry.	Should
MTA.07.02	Statistical monitoring of top related topics	The system to provide a global view of the topics (and how they differ from each other) related to search terms, while at the same time allowing for a deep inspection of the terms most highly associated with each individual topic.	Could
MTA.07.03	Statistical monitoring of top related concepts	The system to provide to the user concept based visualizations which give information about top related concepts to search terms.	Must
MTA.07.04	Compare trend analyses between keywords or hashtags	The system to visualize at the same view trend analyses between keywords or hashtags.	Should
MTA.07.05	Save trend analysis or comparison of trend analyses	The system to enable the user to save trend analysis or comparison of trend analyses and the component's settings which used to produce these results.	Should
MTA.08	Identify social feedbacks	The system to visualize social feedback of products or manufacturers.	Must
MTA.08.01	Aspect based sentiment analysis	The system to visualize, via charts, aspect sentiment analysis for: i) search terms ii) top related concepts to search terms.	Must
MTA.08.02	Statistical monitoring of top related concepts over successive time periods	The system to visualize, via charts, common appearances of search terms and related concepts over successive time periods.	Must
MTA.08.03	Compare social feedback analyses of products or manufacturers	The system to visualize at the same view social feedback analyses between competitive products and competitors.	Must

MTA.08.04	Save social feedback analysis or comparison of social feedback analyses	The system to enable the user to save social feedback analysis or comparison of social feedback analyses and the component's settings in order to produce these results.	Should
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4.1.3.3 Component's operation pre-conditions

- Existence of lexicon for grouping related concepts
- To be defined product attributes to toys
- To be defined added value services to toys

4.1.4 AR Feedback Component Requirements

Component Description

This component allows users of the platform to visualise existing Augmented Reality models and provide comments on those. In more detail, the AR Feedback Component allows:

- Manufacturers to upload Augmented Reality models and prepare them for public/private display to end users
- Manufacturers to setup specific questionnaires linked to Augmented Reality models
- End-users to download Augmented Reality models and visualise them
- End-users to provide comments and answer questionnaires linked to the downloaded Augmented Reality models
- Manufacturers to access comments and questionnaires results.

4.1.4.1 Component's Actors

Name	Description
AR Model Owner	This is the owner of the AR model and the user that initiated the AR Feedback module (typically a manufacturer) and sets it up so it can gather the feedback from the audience
End-User	This is an ordinary user that is presented with the AR model and can basically comment on it and answer some questions.

4.1.4.2 Functional Requirements

ID	Name	Description	MoSCoW
ARF.01	AR uploading	The system to be able to receive an AR model by a user	Must

ARF.01.01	AR Uploading Log	The system to record the owner and the date of upload of an AR model	Must
ARF.01.02	AR Compatibility Check	The system to be able to check the compatibility of the uploaded AR model	Won't
ARF.03	AR Entry editing	The AR model owner to edit the AR model's metadata and accompanying information	Must
ARF.04	AR Entry Updating	The AR model owner to updated an existing AR model	Should
ARF.05	AR Entry Deleting	The AR model owner to delete an already uploaded (by him) AR model	Should
ARF.06	AR Comments Linking	The system to open a commenting session for the AR model	Must
ARF.07	AR Questionnaires Provision	The system to provide a set of questionnaires to the AR model owner	Could
ARF.07.01	AR Questionnaire selection and edit	The AR model owner to select a questionnaire and modify it	Could
ARF.07.02	AR Questionnaire Save	The AR model owner to save a questionnaire	Could
ARF.08	AR Questionnaire Update	The AR model owner to update a questionnaire	Won't
ARF.09	AR Questionnaire Delete	The AR model owner to delete a questionnaire	Could
ARF.10	AR Questionnaires Linking	The system to link questionnaires to the AR models	Must
ARF.11	AR model URL creation	The system to create a download link for each AR model	Must
ARF.12	AR model QR creation	The system to create a QR code for each AR model	Could
ARF.13	AR Model Sharing	The AR model owner to select collaborators and share with them the AR model	Could
ARF.14	AR Model Publishing	The AR model owner to publish openly/set as public his AR model	Must
ARF.15	AR Model Social Sharing	The AR model owner to share the AR model in his social network	Could
ARF.16	AR Model Visualisation	The end-user to initiate the visualisation of an AR model	Must
ARF.17	AR Model Commenting	The end-user to comment on an AR model	Must

ARF.18	AR Model Questionnaire Responding	The end-user to answer on a questionnaire of an AR model	Should
ARF.19	AR Model Screenshot Feedback	The end-user to upload a screenshot of an AR model	Could
ARF.20	AR Model User Social Sharing	The end-user to share the AR model in his social network	Could
ARF.21	AR Comments Viewing	The AR model owner to access the comments on an AR model	Must
ARF.22	AR Questionnaire Results	The AR model owner to access the results of a questionnaire	Should

4.1.4.3 Component's operation pre-conditions

- Availability and compatibility of AR models

4.2 Non-Functional Requirements

The following table shows the not functional requirements pointed out for the Market analytics and trends analysis component, taking into account the eight qualities aforementioned.

Requirement Subcategory	Description
Functional Suitability	The platform and components should be able to support multiple users and to analyse big amount of data in order to provide required outputs to user.
Performance efficiency	The platform and components should be able process data and give required responses to user in a timely and efficient manner.
	The platform and components should be able to guarantee best response times combined with the use of the minimum use of computational resources.
Compatibility	Components should be able to exchange information with other components with ultimate goal: good operation of platform
Usability	The platform and components shall provide a user - friendly interface and user guide with instructions on how to use component and its features.
	The platform and components should support logging about evolution and faults and inform administrators for bugs.

Reliability	The platform and components should be ensured high availability to all types of users
Security	The platform and components should support user identification in order to provide specific accesses to users with limited rights.
	The platform and components should support tracing of user's actions on the component and their execution times
Maintainability	Components must be easily reusable and modular so that the adaptation to changing requirements is possible.
Portability	The platform and components should be able to be deployed on various Operating Systems.
	The platform and components should be able to be deployed in a timely and efficient manner.

5 CONCLUSIONS

5.1 At a glance

D3.1 includes the initial user requirements along with the technical requirements of the ToyLabs platform, by providing also the MVP of the overall infrastructure. The deliverable starts with the presentation of the methodology to be used for the requirements extraction and the MVP definition, acting as a guideline for the whole WP3.

In D3.1, in total **8 actors** were identified¹¹, with **28 Epics** drawn, and out of which **150 user stories** were defined in order to cover the whole ToyLabs methodology and its tools as they have been defined in deliverable D2.1. These resulted to a list of **174 functional** and **12 non-functional** requirements.

The effort put to transform the methodology into elements of the platform, with the large number of user stories generated, showed the challenge the consortium has to face during the 18 months of the project's duration. For that reason, the prioritisation and MVP description to be conducted in the next steps are necessary to drive in a smooth and rapid way the design and implementation of platform.

Feedback from users is necessary to prove that the design and the hypotheses really work, and that software development can be improved. Then, additional features that have been described can help the project evolve, reach mainstreams users and a steady growth rate.

5.2 Next Steps

This document provides input to D3.2 for setting up the system architecture and designing in more detail the identified components, whereas, it also the high-level analysis on which WP4 will base the development phase.

Input taken from pilots in WP5 will refuel Task 3.1 as well as Tasks 3.2, 3.3 and 3.4, and will generate updated versions of the current document (under D3.4 and D3.5) for the last steps of the software to be delivered

Based on the outputs of D3.1, the next steps in ToyLabs are:

- To prioritize the user stories to be used as input to design the components' mock-ups, the system architecture, and the APIs in Deliverable 3.2.

¹¹ Safety and Childhood experts are grouped under 1 actor at this point

- To define the ToyLabs MVP based on the above-mentioned actions, also as part of D3.2. In addition, algorithmic components that need further analysis may be part of further specification analysis in the D3.x deliverables
- To streamline the software development activities of the platform, based on the prioritized user stories and the generated mock-ups, towards delivering the integration plan (D4.1) and finally the initial prototype version of the ToyLabs platform in M11 (D4.2)

